

Integrated germplasm improvement — irrigated

Mukti-CTH1, a rice with cold tolerance and blast resistance for winter and ratoon cropping in Karnataka, India

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More than 700 genotypes from local germplasm and entries of the International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were screened at the UAS research stations, Bangalore. The work to develop cold-tolerant and blast-resistant varieties was done in collaboration with IRRI and the Indian Council of Agricultural Research.

Under natural conditions, the cultivars CTH1, CTH3, and CTH4 were identified as tolerant of cold and resistant to blast, besides being nonlodging. During a 1986 winter trial at Bangalore, CTH1 (B2983b-SR-85-3-2-4 from Indonesia, derived from Sirendah Merah/IR2153-159-1-4) was outstanding. It has 90-100 cm plant height and medium slender grain type. It has been in multilocation trials and in farm trials in Sep and Oct plantings in the southern districts of Karnataka. As IET 11220, it was in All India Coordinated Trial (AICT) for hills. Its blast score at Ponnampet was 3, compared with 7 for Intan.

Under winter conditions, CTH1 yielded 1.3-4.3 t/ha, against 0.0-2.5 t/ha of the best local or currently grown winter variety. It ranked first in 10 plantings in Bangalore and was the only variety to produce some yield (3.2 t/ha) when planted in Oct at Nagenahalli. It ranked second in two of five locations in the hill region in the AICT. CTH1 matures 125-130 d from sowing. Its cooking quality is good and the grain is reportedly very good for puffed rice. Its kernel is red and falls under mid-fine category. Its excellent ratooning ability is yet another potential that can be exploited. ■

Divya (WGL 44645), a newly released rice variety for gall midge (GM) endemic areas

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Divya (WGL 44645), derived from WGL 23022/Surekha, is a short-duration (125-130 d) rice variety, suitable for year-round cultivation. It has the gall midge *Orseolia oryzae* Wood-Mason resistance from Eswarakora in WGL 23022 (CR44/W 12708) and from Siam 29 in Surekha (IR8/Siam 29). With its high resistance (zero infestation at 8 of 10 sites), Divya is suitable for GM (biotype I) endemic areas.

Divya is semidwarf with compact plant type, photoperiod-insensitivity, fertilizer-responsiveness, and grain yield potential

of 6.0 t/ha. The kernel is long slender (length:breadth = 4.21) with no abdominal white.

In 1981-86 trials, Divya gave consistently high yields (see table). During 1988 wet season, it ranked first at the Directorate of Rice Research (DRR), Hyderabad Centre; third at Agricultural Research Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad; and ninth among 64 entries in the preliminary variety trial 2 of DRR. During 1989 wet season, Divya ranked first at Pondicherry, fourth at Pattambi, and fifth at Mandya and at 8 other sites among 15 entries, and was superior to Vikas and Ratna in the uniform variety trial 2 of DRR.

It gave higher grain yield than checks in multilocation trials (1983, 1984) and minikit trials (1985-88) at different sites in Andhra Pradesh. It is popular among farmers of the Northern Telangana Zone. ■

Performance of Divya (WGL 44645) in yield trials at ARS, Warangal, India.

Variety	Yield (t/ha)						Mean
	1981	1982	1983	1984	1985	1986	
Divya (WGL 44645)	4.8	4.5	4.1	4.3	4.0	4.2	4.2
Pothana	3.2	-	-	-	-	-	3.2
Telia Hamsa	-	2.7	-	-	-	-	2.7
Vijay Mahsuri	-	-	3.4	3.2	2.3	3.8	3.2
LSD (0.05)	0.7	0.4	0.3	0.5	0.4	0.2	
% increase over check	29.3	52.5	21.4	33.6	73.9	10.7	

Chaite 4, a short-duration, high-yielding rice variety for double-cropped areas in Nepal

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Nearly 90% of the total rice area of Nepal is located in the tropical to subtropical region; two crops of rice are grown with assured irrigation, followed by one winter crop. The first rice crop, known as *Chaite dhan*, is

planted in Mar in the southern plain area (the Tarai).

Farmers in the inner Tarai and river basin areas (altitude 250-1,000 m) in the mid-hills start seeding the first week of Feb. The early season rice crop (Feb/Mar to Jun/Jul) is followed by the main season rice crop (Jun/Jul to Oct/Nov). Intermediate-tall, traditional type rice variety CH45 (China 45) is the most widely planted. Short-duration rice varieties are needed for the *Chaite dhan* crop, to allow timely planting of main season rice.

Recently released semidwarf rice variety Chaite 4 (IR9729-67-3), a cross of BG34-8/IR28//IR2095-625-1-252, and CH45, along with other test entries, were evaluated in multilocation trials in agricultural research stations and farmers' fields in the Tarai, inner Tarai, and river basin areas of the mid-hills Feb/Mar to Jun/Jul 1989.

Chaite 4 had a duration similar to that of CH45 in both the Tarai and the mid-hill regions. It produced an average 4.7 t/ha, 25% higher than CH45, with better yield performance at all sites (see table).

Chaite 4 has slender, medium-size grain with acceptable cooking and eating quality, is resistant to bacterial leaf blight and blast, and has longer grain dormancy than CH45. ■

Performance of Chaite 4 in on-station (Coordinated Varietal Trial) and on-farm trials at agricultural research stations, and farmers' field trial during 1989 Chaite dhan season.

Site	Tarai region (5 sites on-station ^a and 2 sites on-farm ^b)			Inner Tarai and river basin areas (2 sites on-station ^c and 4 sites on-farm ^d)			Mean			Yield increase (%) over CH45
	Grain yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Crop duration (d)	Plant height (cm)	
	<i>Chaite 4</i>									
On-station	4.5	122	82	4.0	153	78	4.4	132	81	22
On-farm	5.4	125	—	4.9	144	—	5.0	137	—	29
Mean	4.7	123	82	4.6	147	78	4.7	134	81	25
	<i>CH45</i>									
On-station	3.7	123	114	3.4	154	104	3.6	131	111	—
On-farm	3.4	130	—	4.2	139	—	3.9	136	—	—
Mean	3.6	125	114	3.9	144	104	3.7	133	111	—

^aKankai (altitude 90 m), Tarahara (100 m), Hardinath (93 m), Parwanipur (115 m), and Bhairahdwa (105 m) agricultural research stations. ^bJhapa (90 m) and Dhanusha (93 m). ^cGhorlekharka (600 m) area of Pakhribas Agriculture Center and Tapu (1000 m) area of Lumle Agriculture Center. ^d2 sites in Chitawan (256 m), Yampa Phant Tanahu (475 m), and Tapu (1000 m).

Jingmazhan, a high-yielding, good quality indica rice for China

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Jingmazhan, a new superlong, large-grain rice variety released in Guizhou Province, has been awarded the prize for high quality production by the Chinese Ministry of Agriculture.

The variety was developed from (Reimei/Gui 630)B₃F₄//Zun 7201. Reimei is a japonica variety from Japan; Gui 630 and Zun 7201 are Guizhou native indica type cultivars.

Jingmazhan is now planted in 35,000 ha. Jingmazhan is 100 cm tall with 149-d duration, good plant type, and heavy tillering ability. Its 1,000-grain weight is 30.4 g and yield, 7.5 t/ha. Jingmazhan is moderately resistant to blast, sheath blight, cold temperature, and drought.

Appearance, milling recovery, chemical properties, and cooking and eating quality meet the China National Index for high quality rice. Grain length is 7.5 mm, with 3:1 length-to-breadth ratio. Hulling recovery is 79.5%; milling recovery, 72.8%; and head rice recovery, 56.3%. Its grain is translucent, with 18.08% amylose, 8.0% protein content, low-gelatinization temperature (7.0 alkali spreading value), and medium gel consistency (60 mm). ■

Integrated germplasm improvement—upland

Promising upland rice varieties for the North West Province of Cameroon

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Upland rice is cultivated as a subsistence food crop in areas with altitudes of 600-1200 m. Farmers tend to cultivate tall, low-tillering, upland varieties and, in some cases, irrigated varieties in the uplands. Trials at

Babungo (1150 m) and Befang (700 m) in the last 4 yr sought to identify adapted, high-yielding, disease-tolerant varieties with good grain quality.

Both sites have fertile and free-draining soils. Because of its higher altitude, Babungo has lower temperatures. Cultural practices at both sites were similar.

Performance of promising upland rice varieties in North West Cameroon.^a

Genotype	Babungo			Befang		
	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering (DAS)	Av yield (t/ha)	Plant ht (cm)	Days to 50% flowering (DAS)	Av yield (t/ha)
IRAT109	74	108	3.8	75	89	4.1
IRAT112	76	102	3.8	80	80	3.8
M55 (check)	102	125	3.7	108	96	3.0
ITA208	86	123	3.5	88	94	4.3
ROK16	116	125	2.9	119	99	3.7

^aData averaged over 4 yr (1985-88). DAS = days after sowing.